

REVIEW ARTICLE

A SCIENTIFIC REVIEW ON PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIONS OF
MACROTYLOMA UNIFLORUM ON VARIOUS DISEASESAverineni Ravi Kumar*¹, P Gopi² and M Rama Krishna Reddy³DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14257548>**Author affiliation:**¹Department of
Pharmacognosy and
Phytochemistry,²Department of³Department of
PharmaceuticalChemistry Pharmacy
Practice,Nimra College of
Pharmacy, Vijayawada
521456 AP INDIA***E-mail:**karavi315@gmail.com© **Copyright:** 2024 |This is an open access
article under the terms
of the Bhumi
Publishing, India**ABSTRACT:**

Macrotyloma uniflorum plant comes under the family Fabaceae (Leguminosae), which common name is famous in Andhra Pradesh India as Ulavalu. It distributes to all over the world mainly in Africa, Australia and Asia. Mostly it is available as feed for animals (horse gram). This plant contains some disease controlling properties mainly for asthma, liver problems, urinary problems, skin diseases, diabetes, obesity and ulcers. This documentation work may be beneficial for the persons who are suffering from above diseases and at the same time or the plant researchers for its cultivation process [1].

KEYWORDS: *Macrotyloma uniflorum*, *Leguminosae*, *Pharmacology***INTRODUCTION:**

Macrotyloma uniflorum is the plant one of the lesser known beans, commonly called Horse gram. The horse gram is normally used to feed horses, though it is also commonly used in cooking and it is useful as an ayurvedic medicine as it having a food with medicinal qualities. The plant parts of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* roots, leaves, seeds, and in some cases whole plant is used as a medicine and it is belonging to the family Fabaceae or Leguminosae of genus *Macrotyloma* [2].

TAXONOMICAL CLASSIFICATION [3]:**Table 1: Taxonomical classification of *M. uniflorum***

Kingdom	Plantae
Clade	Angiosperms
Clade	Eudicots
Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Genus	Macrotyloma
Species	<i>M. uniflorum</i>

VERNACULAR NAMES [3]:

Some common names of *M. uniflorum* are represented as in their available areas as follows:

Table 2: Vernacular names of *M. uniflorum*

Name of the State/ Language	Vernacular Name
Punjab	Chana/ Chholey
Telangana, Andhra Pradesh	Ulavalu
Darjeeling, Sikkim (Nepali)	Gahat
Kerala	Muthira/Kuthira
Tamil Nadu	Kaanam/Kollu
Maharashtra	Kulith
Karnataka	Hurali
South Canara (Karnataka)	Kudu
Odisha	Kolatha
Northern India	Gahat/Kulath
Himachal Pradesh	Kulath
Myanmar	Bazat
Hindi	Monga

TAXONOMICAL CHARACTERIZATION [4]:**Figure 1: *M. uniflorum* plant, seeds and flower**

Horse gram is a short day, twining, succulent, annual climbing herb which has trifoliate leaves, white colored flowers, long linear pubescent pods with curved beak, flattened small seeds with light red, brown, grey, black or mottled test with photo and thermo-sensitive nature. It matures in 4 to 6 months. Horse gram germ in a reasonably well in drought- areas with very poor soils.

CULTIVATION REQUIREMENTS [5]:

It is native to the old-world tropics and indigenous to India. Archaeological investigations have revealed the use of horse gram as food especially in India as origin around 2000 BC. Horse gram belongs to the genus *Macrotyloma* and contains 25 species indigenous to Africa and Asia. Presence of wild or naturalized horse gram is recorded in Africa (Central, East and Southern Africa) and India.

The primary center of origin and use of horse gram as a cultivated plant is in the plain sand hills of low altitude extending south wards in the Western Ghats in South West India. During the Neolithic period, through counter-migration of human beings, its cultivation was diffused to the northern and western parts of the Indian subcontinent. It is generally grown insub- humid to semi-arid climates with annual rainfall 300–600mm, and also with less than 30 cm rainfall as a dry-land crop up to an elevation of 1800 m from mean sea level. The optimum temperature range for it grow this 25°C t o32°C; it can tolerate temperatures upto 40°C, butthe growth rate declines markedly below 20 °C.

FOLKLORE USE [6]:

It is used by the rural people in day-to-day life as a diet, it has been recognized as potential source of protein and other nutrients. It has high nutritional value equivalent to other commonly grown pulse crops in all aspects and also an excellent source of iron, molybdenum and calcium. Horse gram seed contains carbohydrate (57.2% w/w), protein (22% w/w), dietary fiber (5.3% w/w), fat (0.50% w/w), calcium (287 mg), phosphorus (311 mg), iron (6.77 mg) and calories (321kcal) as well as vitamins like thiamine (0.4mg), riboflavin (0.2 mg) and niacin (1.5 mg) per 100 grams of dry matter.

However, several factors like the genotype, soil, fertilizer application, cultural practices, weather and climatic factors, post-harvest handling and storage can directly or indirectly affect the nutritional quality. Horse gram seed is low in fat and is excellent sources of protein, dietary fiber, a variety of micro- nutrients and phytochemicals still it has remained an underutilized food legume, consumed only by the farming communities of inaccessible areas and low-income groups.

PHYTOCHEMICAL REVIEW [7]:

The *M. uniflorum* plant contains some type of constituents. These can be extracted by using some entrants. Which are listed as below table:

Table 3: Phytochemical classification of *M. uniflorum*

S. No.	Type of Constituent Extracted	Type of Exrant	Part of the Plant Used	Ref.
1	Benzeneacetaldehyde	Ethanol	seed	1
2	Benzeneetanamine	Ethanol	seed	2
3	L-phenylalanine, ethylester	Ethanol	seed	3
4	2-(1-methyl-2-propenyl)bicyclo[2.2.1]heptane	Ethanol	seed	2
5	1H-pyrrole,2-(2,4,6-cycloheptatrienyl)	Ethanol	seed	2
6	Ethyl. Alpha.-dglucopyranoside	Ethanol	seed	4
7	Mome ionositol	Ethanol	seed	4
8	n-Hexadecanoicacid	Ethanol	seed	4
9	Heptadecanoicacid, ethyl ester	Ethanol	seed	5
10	9,12-octadecadienoicacid(Z,Z)	Ethanol	seed	7
11	Ethyl(9Z,12Z)-9,12-octadecadienoate	Ethanol	seed	8
12	Heptadecane,3-methyl	Ethanol	seed	9
13	Octanamide,N-(2-hydroxyethyl)(Z,Z)	Ethanol	seed	10
14	3-cyclopentylpropionicacid, 2- dimethylaminoethyl ester	Ethanol	seed	11
15	(R)14-methyl-8-hexadecn-1-0l	Ethanol	seed	4
16	Hexadecanoicacid,2-hydroxy-1-(hydroxyl methyl) ethyl ester	Ethanol	seed	5
17	1-cyclohexyldimethylsilyloxybutane	Ethanol	seed	6
18	Eicosane	Ethanol	seed	7
19	9,12-Octadecadienoicacid (Z,Z)-,2,3- dihydroxypropyl ester	Ethanol	seed	8
20	Heneicosane	Ethanol	seed	6
21	9-Methyk-10,12-hexadecaduen-1-olacetate	Ethanol	seed	7
22	Hexatriacontane	Ethanol	seed	8
23	i-propyl,9,12-octadecenadienoate	Ethanol	seed	9
24	Vitamin E	Ethanol	seed	9
25	Tricycle[20.8.0.0(7,16)]triacontane,1(22),7(16)- diepoxy	Ethanol	seed	8
26	Stigmasterol	Ethanol	seed	9
27	Stigmast-5-en-3-ol	Ethanol	seed	11
28	(-)-Isolongifolol, acetate	Ethanol	seed	11

PHARMACOLOGICAL REVIEW:

M. uniflorum plant exhibits different types of pharmacological activities. They may be isolated from different plant parts upon treated with some entrants. These can be described in below table.

Table 4: Pharmacological View of *M. uniflorum*

S.No.	Pharmacological Action	Model	Species Used	Plant Parts Used	Extract	Ref.
1	Antimicrobial potency	Inhibition of microbial growth by the disc diffusion method	Gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria	Powdered plant	Ethanol extract	8
2	Hemolytic activity	Spectroscopic methods	Mice erythrocytes.	Aerialparts	Methyl ester of hexadecanoic and ethyl ester of hexadecanoic acid mixture (i) and n- exadecanoicacid	9
3.	Cytotoxicity	Brine shrimp lethality bioassay technique	Brine shrimp nauplii	Aerialparts	Fractionated crude extracts dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, 1-butanol	10
4	Antioxidant activity	Nitric-oxide radical scavenging assay, hydroxyl radical method and phosphomolybdenum reduction assay	Invitro	Dryseeds	Ethanol seed extracts	11
5	Diureticeffect	Lipschitzmethod	Albinorats	Dryseeds	Ethanol seed extracts	12
6	Lithogenesis	Autoanalyzer, Anovafollowedby tukey-kramer	Wistaralbino mice	Seed	Methanolic,acetone	13

7	Antidiabetic effect	Kinetic studies (streptozotocin-nicotinamide-induced diabetic mice)	Swissalbino male mice	Seedmeal	Physiological saline (0.145 m NaCl) and Ammonium sulfate	14
8	Hepato protective activity	Paracetamol and d-galactosamine induced liver toxicity	Albinorats	Seeds	Methanol	15
9	Anti hypercholesterolemic effect	High-fat diet-induced hypercholesterolemia	Sprague-dawley rats	Seeds	Thanol and water extract	16

ANALYTICAL REVIEWS:

The *M. uniflorum* plant contains some analytes, these can be extracted by doing different methods. These can be listed below.

Table 5: Analytical review of *M. uniflorum* Effects

S.No	Analyte Name	Compounds of Analyte	Method Used	Extract Name	Ref.
1	Phenolic acids	3, 4-dihydroxy benzoic, <i>p</i> -hydroxy benzoic, vanillic, caffeic, <i>p</i> -coumeric, ferulic, syringic and sinapic acids	Reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography (rp- hplc) with UV detection	Acetonitrile or methanol).	17
2	Linoleic acid	Mome inositol, ethyl alpha-d-glucopyranoside, n- hexadecanoic acid	Gc-msspectroscopy	Ethanol extract	18
3	Quercetin	Rutin and Gallic acid	HPTLC	Toluene: Ethyl Acetate:Formic Acid:Methanol (3:6:1.6:0.4) solution	19

CONCLUSION:

Macrotyloma uniflorum plant which is commonly famous used as horse gram. Which contains fibre and protein contents. It is used as horse feed and some ayurvedic preparations for treating the various diseases in humans. It contains different types of analytical constituents, by using this constituents scientists formed the ayurvedic preparations. Mainly this review useful for the knowing the scientific and pharmacological actions of the *Macrotyloma uniflorum* to the researchers who continued their research works upon this plant.

REFERENCES:

1. Tropical Forages. (n.d.). *Macrotyloma uniflorum*. Available at: <http://www.tropicalforages.info/key/forages/Media/Html/entities/macrotylomauniflorum.htm>
2. Wikipedia Contributors. (n.d.). *Macrotyloma uniflorum*. Wikipedia. Available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Macrotyloma_uniflorum
3. Sampath Kumar, T., Muthusamy, P., Radha, R., & Ilango, K. (2019). Review on phytochemical, pharmacological, and pharmacognostical profile of horse gram. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 8(5), 1436–1449.
4. Sampath Kumar, T., Muthusamy, P., Radha, R., & Ilango, K. (2019). Review on phytochemical, pharmacological, and pharmacognostical profile of horse gram. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 8(5), 1436–1449.
5. Sampath Kumar, T., Muthusamy, P., Radha, R., & Ilango, K. (2019). Review on phytochemical, pharmacological, and pharmacognostical profile of horse gram. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 8(5), 1436–1449.
6. Bhartiya, A., Aditya, J. P., & Kant, L. (2015). Nutritional and remedial potential of an underutilized food legume horsegram (*Macrotyloma uniflorum*). *The Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences*, 25(4), 908–920.
7. Das, S., Vasudeva, N., & Sharma, S. (2014). Chemical composition of ethanol extract of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* (Lam.) Verdc. Using GC-MS spectroscopy. *Journal of Organic and Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, 4(1), 13.
8. Kawsar, S. M. A., Uddin, M. S., Huq, E., Nahar, N., & Ozeki, Y. (2008). Biological investigation of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* Linn. extracts against some pathogens. *Journal of Biological Sciences*, 8(6), 1051–1056.
9. Kawsar, S. M. A., Mostafa, G., Huq, E., Nahar, N., & Ozeki, Y. (2009). Chemical constituents and hemolytic activity of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* L. *International Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 3(1), 42–48.
10. Kawsar, S. M. A., Huq, E., & Nahar, N. (2008). Cytotoxicity assessment of the aerial parts of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* Linn. *International Journal of Pharmacology*, 4(4), 297–300.
11. Ravishankar, K., & Vishnu Priya, P. S. (2012). Antioxidant activity of ethanolic seed extracts of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* and *Cucumis melo* for therapeutic potential. *International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Chemistry*, 2(2), 442.

12. Ravishankar, K., & Vishnu Priya, P. S. (2012). Evaluation of diuretic effect of ethanolic seed extracts of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* and *Cucumis melo* in rats. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biological Sciences*, 3(3), 251–255.
13. Bigoniya, P., Bais, S., & Sirohi, B. (2014). The effect of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* seed on bile lithogenicity against diet-induced cholelithiasis in mice. *Ancient Science of Life*, 33(4), 242–251.
14. Gupta, L. H., Badole, S. L., Bodhankar, S. L., & Sabharwal, S. G. (2010). Antidiabetic potential of α -amylase inhibitor from the seeds of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* in streptozotocin-nicotinamide-induced diabetic mice. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Biology*, 49(2), 182–189.
15. Parmar, H. B., Das, S. K., & Gohil, K. J. (2012). Hepatoprotective activity of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* seed extract on paracetamol and d-galactosamine-induced liver toxicity in albino rats. *International Journal of Pharmacological Research*, 2(2), 86–91.
16. Sathis Kumar, D., Prashanthi, G., Avasarala, H., & Banji, D. (2013). Antihypercholesterolemic effect of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* (Lam.) Verdc. (Fabaceae) extract on high-fat diet-induced hypercholesterolemia in Sprague-Dawley rats. *Journal of Dietary Supplements*, 10(2), 116–128.
17. Kawsar, S. M. A., Huq, E., Nahar, N., & Ozeki, Y. (2008). Identification and quantification of phenolic acids in *Macrotyloma uniflorum* by reversed-phase HPLC. *American Journal of Plant Physiology*, 3(4), 165–172.
18. Das, S., Vasudeva, N., & Sharma, S. (2014). Chemical composition of ethanol extract of *Macrotyloma uniflorum* (Lam.) Verdc. Using GC-MS spectroscopy. *Organic and Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, 4, 13.
19. Reddy, J., & Koumaravelou, K. (2018). HPTLC analysis of hydroalcoholic extracts of *Clerodendrum viscosum* V. leaves and *Macrotyloma uniflorum* L. seeds. *International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 9(1), 194–200.